

BAPTISM OF THE HOLY SPIRIT

By

Prasanna Kumar Monditoka M.Div., M.Pharm.

INTRODUCTION

The account of the baptism of the Holy Spirit began with John the Baptist in the New Testament. John the Baptist pointed out that Jesus Christ will baptize his disciples with the Holy Spirit. He declared, “I have baptized you with water, but he will baptize you with the Holy Spirit (Mark 1:8, ESV).” The baptism of the Holy Spirit is qualitatively different from the baptism with water, both by means of agency and physicality. Now, what is this baptism of the Holy Spirit? Is it a regenerative baptism (1 Cor 12:13) or supernatural empowerment of the Holy Spirit (Acts 1:4-5)? Or is it a baptism apart from the regeneration?

After the emergence of Pentecostalism and Charismatic movement, the notion of the second experience of the baptism of the Holy Spirit came into prominence.¹ On the other hand, some evangelicals hold that the baptism of the Holy Spirit occurs at the conversion.² In this paper, I argue that there are two different uses of the word “baptism of the Holy Spirit” in the New Testament and they communicate two different experiences and two different purposes.³ In 1 Corinthians 12:13, Paul mentioned that—in one spirit we were all baptized—to denote the regenerative baptism of the Holy Spirit. However, in Acts 1:4-5, Luke used the word “baptism of the Holy Spirit” to refer to the supernatural empowerment of the Holy Spirit in the Apostolic period.⁴ In this paper, first I will provide my view on the baptism of the Holy Spirit with biblical

¹ Wayne A. Grudem, *Systematic Theology: An Introduction to Biblical Doctrine* (Leicester, England: InterVarsity Press, 1994), 766.

² Grudem, *Systematic Theology*, 768, 773.

³ John Piper, “What is the Baptism of the Holy Spirit,” *Desiring God* (blog), September 14, 2021, <https://www.desiringgod.org/interviews/what-is-the-baptism-of-the-holy-spirit>.

⁴ John Piper argued in his blog that there are two uses of the word “baptism of the Holy Spirit.” He maintained that the first use of the word in 1 Corinthians 12:13 refers to the receiving of the Spirit at conversion and the second use of the word in Acts 1:4-5 refers to the empowerment by the Spirit and it occurs multiple times in a

and theological justification, delayed reception of the Holy Spirit, and then I will explain why and how I disagree with the Pentecostals and Wayne A. Grudem and Gregg R. Allison.

Baptism of the Holy Spirit in the New Testament

First, the authors of the New Testament used the word “baptism of the Holy Spirit” to refer two different experiences i.e., regenerative baptism of the Holy Spirit (1 Cor 12:13) and special empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit in the Apostolic period (Acts 1:4-5).⁵

Regenerative Baptism of the Holy Spirit

In the first use, the regenerative work of the Holy Spirit was reckoned as the baptism of the Holy Spirit. In 1 Corinthians 12:13, Paul mentioned that—in one Spirit, we were all baptized—and he pointed out the regenerating work of the Holy Spirit in uniting us to Christ and the body of the church. Here, God the Holy Spirit is granting people a new experience of life at conversion. It happened to all the Corinthians when they became Christians, and it happens to all the Christians.⁶ This is in line with other scriptures which talk about regenerating work of the Holy Spirit. In Titus 3:5, Paul mentioned that we are saved by the regeneration and renewal work of the Holy Spirit at our conversion. In 1 Corinthians 12:3, Paul pointed out that no one can affirm the Lordship of Jesus without the aid of the Holy Spirit.

Special Empowering Baptism of the Holy Spirit in the Apostolic period

In the second use, the baptism of the Holy Spirit refers to two aspects: the arrival/outpouring of the Holy Spirit at the inauguration of the new covenant age, accompanied

-believer’s life. However, I maintain that the baptism of the Holy Spirit in Acts 1:4-5 refers to the unusual supernatural empowerment of the Holy Spirit in the Apostolic period, therefore, I maintain that it will not continue.

⁵ Piper, “What is the Baptism of the Holy Spirit.”

⁶ Grudem, *Systematic Theology*, 767.

by the supernatural unusual empowerment for the gospel witness in the apostolic period. The fresh and unprecedented arrival of the Holy Spirit resulted in the outburst of the new covenant age with the outpouring of the Spirit, the explosion of gifts, and a new empowerment of the disciples for the missions.

In Acts 1:4-8, the resurrected Jesus promised the disciples that they will be baptized with the Holy Spirit in the upcoming days. It is evident that here Jesus referred to an unusual supernatural outpouring of the Holy Spirit on the disciples which empowers them to be witnesses in Jerusalem, and in all Judea and Samaria, and to the end of the earth. This empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit is different from the regenerative baptism of the Holy Spirit because the disciples were already regenerated and followed Christ before they were empowered (Matthew 16:16-17).⁷ In the similar line, the disciples in the early church were first born-again before they receive the outpouring or empowering or gift or baptism of the Holy Spirit (Acts 8:12, 14-17; 19:1,6). It points out that regeneration or salvation is the background or prerequisite to receiving the empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit in the Apostolic period.⁸ God promised that he will pour out his Spirit on all humanity (Joel 2:28-29). John the Baptist prophesied that Jesus Christ baptizes his disciples with the Holy Spirit (Matt 3:11, Mark 1:8, Luke 3:16, and John 1:32-34). This is in line with the instructions of Jesus to his disciples to wait for the outpouring of the Holy Spirit who will strengthen and equip them for his mission. He promised his disciples that he will send the promise of Father and he instructed them to stay in the city until they are clothed from on high i.e., baptized by the Holy Spirit (Luke 24:49, Acts 1:5). This baptism of the Holy Spirit refers to the outpouring of the Holy Spirit with might, power, and force at the dawn of the new

⁷ Grudem, *Systematic Theology*, 769.

⁸ John Rodman Williams, *Renewal Theology: Systematic Theology from a Charismatic Perspective*. (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 1996), 188-189.

covenant age. The anticipated outpouring of the Holy Spirit fell upon the disciples on the day of Pentecost, and they were all filled with the Holy Spirit (Acts 2:1-4).⁹ As inspired by the Spirit, Peter preached the gospel and confirmed that this is the fulfillment of the promise and outpouring of the Spirit (Acts 2:33).

The special empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit did not continue after the period of the apostles as it served the purpose of witnessing the message of the gospel proclaimed by the apostles (Heb 2:24). There are at least three or four special events in Acts (Acts 2:1-4, 8:14-17, 10, and 19:1-6). However, there is no mention of the special empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit in the epistles and apostles did not give a normative principle to the church. Although Paul mentions the baptism in the Spirit in 1 Corinthians 12:13 which does not refer to a special empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit (as in the case of Acts 1:4-5), rather, it refers to the regenerating baptism of the Spirit. In the epistles, Christians are encouraged to be filled by the Spirit (Eph 5:18) and empowered by the Spirit (Rom 15:13, Eph 3:16), however, the context does not suggest a special empowering baptism of the Spirit, rather, it suggests that believers should sing psalms and hymns and grow in their faith, love, and hope. Therefore, it is safe to conclude that the special empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit is not normative for all believers. Instead, we are born again by the regenerative baptism of the Spirit (1 Cor 12:13), and we should seek to be filled with the Spirit so that we give thanks and grow in love, faith, and hope (Rom 15:13, Eph 3:16).

Delayed Reception of the Holy Spirit

There were some instances of unusual experiences of the baptism of the Holy Spirit recorded in Acts (8:14-17 and 19:1-6). In Acts 8:14-17, it is evident that the new converts in

⁹ Allison and Köstenberger, *The Holy Spirit*, 388.

Samaria received the gift of special empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit after the apostles laid their hands on them. In Acts 19:1-6, the author mentioned that the disciples were not baptized in the name of Jesus, and they did not aware of the Holy Spirit. Therefore, it is safe to conclude that they were not regenerated before Paul met them. When Paul met them, they were baptized again, and they received the gift of the special empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit. Based on these two incidents, it is safe to conclude that the special empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit is for the purpose of affirming the witness of the apostles.

Interaction with Different Views and Response to the Claims of Second Experience

In this paper, I argued that there are two different uses of the word “baptism of the Holy Spirit”: 1) regenerative (1 Cor 12:13) and 2) special empowering/outpouring in the Apostolic period (Acts 1:4-5). In contrary to the understanding of Allison and Grudem, I agree with the interpretation of the Pentecostals in distinguishing the special empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit from regeneration.¹⁰ However, I restrict this fulfillment to the Apostolic period. Therefore, I argue that there is no necessity for Christians to expect another empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit in the current age. However, I still maintain that Christians enjoy the presence and blessings of the Spirit due to the arrival and empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit. God the Holy Spirit is with us to grant us the regenerating baptism and to comfort, guide, fill, correct, sanctify, and lead us we anticipate the return of Christ, and he will transform us and glorify us in the second coming of Christ. I agree with Grudem and Allison that we should not require Christians to have a second experience of the baptism of the Holy Spirit to avoid the danger of two groups of Christians. However, we should be gracious to our Pentecostal brothers who claim

¹⁰ Williams, *Renewal Theology*, 188-189.

that they have a second experience of the baptism of the Holy Spirit. I would consider those experiences as the moments of filling of the Holy Spirit or a new empowering work of the Holy Spirit in their life.¹¹ In any case, I will be respectful to them and encourage them to be filled with the Holy Spirit.

¹¹ Grudem, *Systematic Theology*, 769.

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